

Psychological Research of Ethnic Prejudices

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Abstract—In the article the experience of principle new technology development of ethnopsychological experiment on the basis of using other virtual independent experimental variables is presented. It is shown that ethnic prejudices are the result of forming and development of specific semantic barriers, arising up in the conditions of interethnic co-operation and people's communication. Their overcoming is more successful in the conditions of the special organized process of teaching in a polyethnic environment, characteristic for the modern institute

Keywords—virtual monoethnic group, semantic barrier, general fund of semantic notions, polyethnic environment, ethnic prejudices

I. INTRODUCTION

IN connection with a growth of problems of interethnic relations a lead through of the special ethnopsychological researches in modern society is actual. Especially it is important for a youth in polyethnic terms.

In this context the task to carry out a psychological research of ethnic prejudices in the experimental groups of students in institutes of the Republic of Kazakhstan was put.

Because of increased difficulties, connected with the detection and measuring of the ethnically determined human personality features, revealed in the process of communication and co-operation of people in a polyethnic environment, the special method of experimental research was developed. The basic idea of this method consists of design of virtual monoethnic groups.

II. DESIGN OF EXPERIMENT

On the first stage, testing of all of examinees with the purpose of exposure «original Kazakhs» and «original Russians» is conducted. In spite of seeming absurdity of purpose, majority the tested with enthusiasm filled the ethnopsychological questionnaire, which contained 19 questions, reflecting the way of life and culture of different peoples. Research was conducted anonymously. Questions were formulated as assertions. Respondent was to mark judgments which he agrees with.

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Additional motivation of experiment participants` activity was provided with a report that on the results of the first stage the limited amount of examinee will be selected for participating in the subsequent series of research, organized in form of intensive lessons, allowing in a short space of time to capture abilities and skills of effective interethnic communication. The special role of such communication for the future professional growth of young specialist in the conditions of polyethnic Kazakhstan was underlined.

The second stage of research was begun with a selection for participating in further experiments of three experimental and three control sub-groups of examinee for 12 persons in each. This amount of people in sub-groups is optimum from point of organization of group teaching employment, allowing in a maximal measure to utilize the phenomena of interpersonality co-operation and communication with the purpose of increase the efficiency of joint cognitive activity.

To the examinee of the first two subgroups of experimental and control group it was emphasized that men and girls, meeting the criteria of «original Kazakhs» and «original Russians», on the basis of results of testing which was conducted on the first stage of experiment with all of examinee were selected there. Consequently, «original Kazakhs» entered in the sub-groups of MKE (monoethnic Kazakh experimental) and MKK (monoethnic Kazakh control), in the sub-groups of MRE (monoethnic Russian experimental) and MRK (monoethnic Russian control) «original Russians». Actually all of monoethnic subgroups are virtual reality, represented in consciousness of participants of experiment as a maximal possible ideal on the parameters ethnic group to which they have the honor to belong.

As actually selection of both original Kazakhs and original Russians is practically an impracticable task, in these subgroups the representatives of Kazakh and Russian ethnoses were taken away in a casual order. The sub-groups of PGE (experimental polyethnic group) and PGK (control polyethnic group) were completed from the representatives of Kazakh and Russian ethnoses for a 6 examinee in each also in a casual order. Quantitative correlation of youths and girls in all of experimental and control sub-groups was equal.

As a matter of fact, on the second stage of research, due to application of virtual independent experimental variables, as virtual monoethnic sub-groups, additional were provided for activation the ethno psychological features of personality, conditioned the awareness of fact of confession of man the valuable and competent member of ethnic group. It is necessary to underline that degree of ethnic authentication with virtual, and that is why the ideal monoethnic group, is much higher, than authentication with the real sub-group. As in polyethnic subgroups no instructions-options were given, the activation of their ethno psychological features of personality had been carried out due to the natural socially-psychological mechanisms of interethnic co-operation and communication.

Thus, monoethnic sub-groups of experimental and control groups in a psychological plan are virtual realities, formed by «unobtrusive suggestion», which afterwards showed in test indexes none the less real than the real polyethnic sub-groups of PGK and PGR.

On the third stage of research the specially organized lessons on development the skills and abilities of interethnic communication were conducted. Thus in an experimental group, consisting of two monoethnic and one polyethnic sub-groups, lessons were conducted with the use of untraditional teaching technologies, developed on the basis of principles of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity [2]. In a control group, also consisting of analogical sub-groups, lessons were conducted through traditional teaching technologies.

The purpose of this stage of research is based on the comparative analysis of degree of influence of traditional and untraditional teaching method, modeled on the type of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, on the ethnically determined personality features. Teaching technology, based on principles of forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, is a complex, consisting of different micro-trainings, in which the psycho technical methods and facilities, adapted to the educational process from the arsenal of modern practical psychology and psychotherapy are used [3].

The lessons in experimental sub-groups were conducted by teachers, using teaching technology, based on principles of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, and being certificated trainers of the Kazakh psychologists association. In control sub-groups the lessons were conducted by teachers, who do not have the special preparation on jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology and who are not trainers in practical psychology area.

III. SUBJECTS AND METHODS

For the lessons in both groups: the experimental and control the identical special course «Psychology of interethnic communication» was conducted. 72 students of 1-3 courses, joined in 6 groups for 12 persons in each took part in research.

The diagnostics of dynamics process of display the psychological student's personality features in forming and development the cognitive activity was carried out twice. The first series of measuring by means of adapted test of self-concept by V.V. Stolin [1, 5], was conducted in control and experimental groups before lessons on the special course «Psychology of interethnic communication». The second series of measuring was conducted after these lessons. The special procedure of experimental research with the use of virtual independent variables allows to «adjust» an ordinary personality questionnaire for determination of changes of ethnopsychological personality features in the process of teaching.

IV. RESULTS

Results are taken to the following. The change of ethnic prejudices was rationed in the process of forming and development of cognitive activity. In order that to check up a hypothesis about the changes of ethnopsychological component of psychological features of students` personality

in the conditions of teaching on the basis of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology by comparison to teaching on the basis of traditional teaching technologies, the analysis of research results, got on the basis of conducted test of self-concept by V.V. Stolin was held (results are shown below in a table I).

TABLE I
MEAN VALUES OF INDEXES OF SUB-GROUPS EXAMINEE «BEFORE AND AFTER»
TEACHING

Groups of examinee	Measuring	With	F1	F2	FZ	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
MKE	1	19,6	9,2	7,7	4,7	4,1	5,4	4,3	6,4	4,8	2,5
	2	26,8	15,5	9,0	7,6	3,8	5,6	5,1	7,2	4,9	2,6
MRE	1	18,5	8,3	9,9	5,4	3,7	5,3	4,2	6,8	4,3	2,4
	2	25,7	13,7	10,3	8,5	3,8	4,9	5,3	7,5	4,4	2,5
PGE	1	19,3	10,2	8,7	4,9	3,8	5,3	4,4	6,5	4,8	2,4
	2	23,5	15,0	10,1	5,2	4,1	5,5	4,5	7,6	4,7	2,5
MKK	1	18,3	8,1	8,6	4,7	3,4	5,2	4,5	6,2	4,2	2,4
	2	20,2	7,8	8,3	5,3	3,5	5,4	4,6	6,3	4,3	2,6
MRK	1	19,5	9,2	11,6	4,8	4,1	5,4	4,5	6,3	4,7	2,3
	2	19,8	9,6	12,8	5,1	4,2	5,5	4,6	4,9	4,3	2,5
GK	1	20,2	7,7	10,0	5,4	3,5	4,8	4,1	4,8	4,3	2,6
	2	19,6	8,1	9,8	5,6	3,7	5,0	4,2	5,0	4,2	2,7

Denotations: C- global self-concept, F1-self-esteem, F2-autosympathy, FZ-self-confidence, F4-a selfconsistency, F5 - self-acceptance, F6 - self-accusation, F7 -relation, expected from other, F8 - self interest, F9 - self-comprehension. Groups examinee marked in a text

From an analysis, presented in a table 1 is shown that increase of index C (global self-concept) observed in the sub-groups of MKE (t=3,4), MRE (t=3,5) and PGE (t=3,2) at probability of possible error of p>0,01. Thus, in the sub-group of PGE increase of positive relation to itself considerably below, than in other experimental sub-groups.

Index of F1-self-esteem, which testifies to the presence of faith in the forces, capabilities and energies, estimations of the possibilities and respect to itself increased only at examinee of experimental group. The critical values of t-Student's criteria are accordingly evened in sub-groups: MKE (3,3), MRE (3,4) and PGE (3,1) and it is talked that the looked after changes on this index are statistically reliable.

The fact that the increase of F1 index in the monoethnic experimental MKE and MRE sub-groups is considerably higher, than in polyethnic to the experimental PGE sub-group pays its attention. It means that monoethnic (Kazakh and Russian) sub-groups appeared more sensible to influence of technology of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, what polyethnic sub-group. It means that in the polyethnic sub-group of student in the conditions of activation of their cognitive activity by means of untraditional teaching

technologies, there is an intensification of specific semantic barriers. Last, as is generally known, render the braking affecting process of forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, showing up at behavioral level of subject's activity in form of ethnic prejudices [4].

Especially sensible to such influences in these terms is the process of appropriation of every student «general fund of semantic educations» [2]. Violation of this process means the absence of possibilities for personality changes, including those which can prove in the changes of index F1 of self-esteem. It means that index F1 self-esteem on the test of self-concept by V.V.Stolin represents the indicator of presence or absence of ethnic personality prejudices in the conditions of analogical, created in our virtual experiment.

As it was already pointed out the experimental and control groups are presented by the artificial selection of composition 6 sub-groups for 12 persons in each. To the examinee of the first two sub-groups of experimental and control group it was said that in these sub-groups people sneaked up on the basis of complex testing results which was indeed conducted with all of examinee before an experiment. No instructions-options were given thus. These measures had resulted in that the monoethnic sub-groups of experimental and control group in a psychological relation appeared virtual realities, formed by «unobtrusive suggestion».

It is specially needed to underline a fact, consisting of that meaningful increase of F1 index of self-esteem in an experimental group on the whole by comparison to a control group proves that teaching technology, based on principles of forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, renders greater influence on the change of student's personality features, than technology of the traditional teaching, that comes forward as next confirmation of research hypothesis.

An F3 index - self-confidence, interpreted as a faith in the practical capabilities which will be realized in «embodiment in life planned», also increased statistically meaningful appearance in the sub-groups of MKE ($t=3,43$) and MRE ($t=3,34$). In the group of PGE the increase of self-confidence was not found out. It follows from this that personality changes, happened in monoethnic sub-groups (MKE and MRE) in the process of teaching, approximately identical on the index of F3, while in a polyethnic sub-group statistically meaningful changes did not happen on this index. Consequently, we deal with the analogical dynamics of changes of indexes as well as in the previous case with F1. It is therefore possible again to establish that monoethnic (Kazakh and Russian) sub-groups appeared more sensible to influence of technology of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, what polyethnic sub-group on the F3 index. Low sensitiveness of students in polyethnic sub-group to untraditional technologies of teaching similarly can be explained by actualization of ethnic prejudices in these terms.

The coincidence of results, got on the indexes of two different scales of F1 and F3, can testify both to their content-psychological likeness between itself and that hypothesis about actualization of ethnic prejudices in polyethnic experimental groups in the conditions of forming and development of

jointly-dialogic cognitive activity confirmed the next time. It also confirms with that the absence statistically of meaningful changes of indexes of F1 and F3 in polyethnic control sub-groups, where teaching was conducted on the basis of traditional technologies, not assist to forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity.

On a background of the made conclusions a few unexpectedly meaningful changes which showed up at an examinee on the scale of self-accusation of F6 in the sub-groups of MKE ($t=3,38$) and MRE look statistically ($1*3,65$). Present contradiction: along with the increase of self-acceptance and self-esteem there is an increase of opposite index - self-accusations. That in the sub-groups of MKK, MRK, PGK talks about the same, and also PGE the indexes of self-accusation remained at former level. It means that monoethnic experimental groups again appeared sensible to untraditional technologies of teaching, but already on the indexes of opposite in a richly-psychological plan scale.

This contradiction can be the investigation of fall-off of the artificially (virtually) supported high self-appraisal as a result of authentication examinee with «real», that by the best representative of the ethnos. In the real terms of the intensive teaching, by the provided technology of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity which, as is generally known, results in forming and development of reflection thought, an examinee appears before the necessity of awareness of endlessness of cognition process. In same queue, it gives the understanding of scantiness of concrete cognitive activity results, whatever it was great on volume and to man hours. Force of the real awareness of the helplessness in the endless world of knowledge appears so high, that it actually takes to «not» the virtual force of ethnic self-identification.

As it followed from the considered, in the conditions of teaching on the basis of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology it is required to take into account the negative consequences of the formed reflection thinking which assists to the global decline of personality self-appraisal. Thus external stimuli directed on the increase of personality self-appraisal and based on appeals to ethnic superiority are ineffectual. And it means that a teaching process, based on jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology, allows to change student's ethnic prejudices, which are consequence of displays of ethnocentrism, characteristic for monoethnic groups.

Results of F7 scale - relation, expected from other, rotined the highest statistically meaningful change in the sub-group of PGE ($t=3,73$). The index of relation, expected from other changed insignificantly, and in the sub-groups of MKE ($t=3,43$) and MRE ($t=3,48$). It means that polyethnic experimental sub-group appeared the most sensible to jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology on the F7scale, of while monoethnic (Kazakh and Russian) experimental sub-groups appeared less sensible on the same scale.

As in a content-psychological plan the F7 scale is intended for the reflection of changes in heterogeneous on composition group, which is polyethnic sub-group, nothing strange, it would seem, is not present in the got indexes. But if to take into account the change of indexes in polyethnic experimental sub-group on a background of absence of statistically

meaningful changes in polyethnic to the control sub-group on the F7 scale, it testifies that teaching, based on technology of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity, renders the special influence on the ingroup processes of meaning making. To understand this feature, it is necessary to appeal to the results of previous analysis.

As it was set by us before, low sensitiveness of polyethnic sub-group to untraditional teaching technologies, appeared as the result of actualization of ethnic prejudices in these terms. But on the F7 scale we watch a reverse picture, that high sensitiveness of polyethnic sub-group to untraditional teaching technologies, to based on jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology. From it a conclusion about deactualization of ethnic prejudices in the indicated terms must ensue. As we are talking about the same phenomenon, but fixed through different scales, such conclusion logically would be erroneous. Then uniquely faithful conclusion will be a conclusion that the changes of indexes of F7 scale are conditioned by other reasons, than the changes of ethnic prejudices.

To understand these reasons, better to appeal to the psychological mechanisms, lying in basis of process of forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity as a higher level of development of cognitive activity in the teaching process [2]. A few stages are selected in the process of forming and development of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity. First and most essential is the stage of creation the general fund of information during joint students' cognitive activity. The second stage, which begins practically simultaneously with the first, is a process of forming the general fund of semantic educations on the basis of comprehension of general fund of information. On the next stage simultaneously with completion of process of forming the general fund of semantic educations the process of its appropriation by each of participants of joint activity begins. The fourth stage characterized by completion of process of assimilation of general fund of semantic educations by every student is accompanied with a depth personality re-structuring which is revealed at behavioral level as changes of valued orientation, options and persuasions. Afterwards to this list of behavioral displays we added the change of ethnic prejudices, which, to our opinion, are the original concentrated expression of personality re-structuring process in the conditions of polyethnic environment of surroundings.

Taking into account considered it is possible to draw a conclusion that the F7 scale of test on self-concept appeared as most sensible to the initial stages of process of forming the general fund of semantic educations, when a moment of intensive re-structuring personality in polyethnic experimental sub-group did not come. Otherwise speaking, the indexes of F7 scale, reflecting the intermediate results of process general fund forming of semantic formations, appear indifferent to its end-point results, conditioned by re-structuring personalities which show up at behavioral level in the conditions of polyethnic surroundings as changes of ethnic prejudices. From it the conclusion that ethnic prejudices are the phenomena which show the generalized result of process of re-structuring personality ensues. For this reason they require creation of the special terms of research,

necessary for the design of forming process and development of general fund of semantic formations, lying in basis of re-structuring personality in a polyethnic group.

So, the analysis of results of test on self-concept allowed checking up a hypothesis about more considerable changes of ethnopsychological component of students' psychological personality features in the conditions of teaching on the basis of jointly-dialogic cognitive activity technology by comparison to teaching on the basis of traditional teaching technologies. It was thus succeeded not only to prove the legitimacy of hypothesis, but also to expose the psychological maintenance of these features which appeared as ethnic prejudices, and also to specify psychological mechanisms, determining their forming and development. As the last specific semantic barriers, braking the processes of forming and appropriation of general fund of semantic formations in the conditions of joint forms of cognitive students' activity, are acknowledged, which through mechanisms of re-structuring personality show up at behavioral level of subject's activity in form ethnic prejudices.

Indexes of F2-autosympathy, F4-selfconsistency, F5-self-acceptance, F8-self interest and F9-self-comprehension in all of sub-groups examinee appeared statistically not meaningful.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus, the described method of experimental ethnopsychological research allows to use the test scales of traditional psycho diagnostic personality questionnaires as indicators of the ethnopsychological personality phenomena, being consequence of design of virtual experimental monoethnic sub-groups. Thus, as researches results show, the last come forward as independent experimental variables with such degree of representativeness, the consequence of introduction of which is enough reliably fixed as changes of test indexes of dependent variables.

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